

STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES OF MODIFIED STARCHES FOR THE PURPOSE OF THEIR USE IN THE CULINARY PRODUCTS TECHNOLOGY**Mazurenko I.,***doctor of technical sciences, professor
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With the development of economy and the improvement of living standards, consumers' requirements for the food industry are also increasing, not only to eat well, but also to the appearance of food and other quality requirements are higher. Crystal dumpling is one of the representative food of crystal skin pasta. It is widely loved by consumers for its crystal clear appearance and smooth elastic and tough taste. However, for crystal dumpling, because it is made of whole starch, it is easy to crack under the condition of -50°C quick freezing. At the same time, in the process of making crystal dumpling skin, it is easy to crack due to water loss, and it is not easy to roll into shape and the skin is easy to crack. Therefore, it is very urgent to improve the appearance, edible quality and processing performance of crystal dumplings. In view of the fact that modified starch is widely used in dumplings as an improver, it can improve its transparency, water holding capacity, reduce frost cracking rate and cooking loss. Although there are many studies on the application of modified starch in quick-frozen dumplings, the research on the application of modified starch in crystal dumplings is relatively small. In this paper, the effects of the characteristics and processing conditions of four different modified starch on the characteristics of crystal dumpling skin were studied.

Four kinds of modified starches that are expected to improve the quality of crystal dumpling skins were selected, namely Potato acetate starch, Potato hydroxypropyl starch, Octenyl succinate starch sodium, Acetate cassava starch. Through the determination of the physical indicators of the above four modified starches, and then explore the feasibility of applying them to crystal dumpling skins to improve their quality. Studies have found that the light transmittance of the four modified starches is higher than that of the original crystal dumpling mixed starch, which verifies the feasibility of applying these four modified starches to the crystal dumpling skin to improve its transparency and other characteristics. At the same time, it provides a certain reference value for related research on improving the characteristics of crystal dumpling skin.

Keywords: modified starch, organoleptic properties, structure, water-holding capacity, elasticity.

Introduction. At present, there are more than 2000 varieties and specifications of modified starch, which can be divided into physical modified starch, chemical modified starch, enzymatic modified starch and compound modified starch (Wang Qin et al., 2005, p. 19-21). Physical modified starch includes pre gelatinized starch, wet heat treated starch, irradiated starch, mechanically milled starch, etc.; chemical modified starch refers to the modified starch obtained by various chemical reagents, which can be divided into two categories: one is the starch that reduces the molecular weight of starch, such as acid hydrolyzed starch, oxidized starch, dextrin, etc.; the other is the starch that increases the molecular weight of starch, such as esterified starch, etherified starch, cross-linked starch and graft copolymer starch, etc.; enzymatic modified starch refers to the modified starch obtained by biological treatment, including porous starch, enzymatic dextrin, etc.; composite modified starch, modified starch obtained by two or more methods, such as oxidized cross-linked starch, cross-linked esterified starch, etc. According to the different sources of starch, it can be divided into potato modified starch, corn modified starch, cassava modified starch and so on. It can be seen from the above that

the application prospect of modified starch in semi-finished dough is very broad.

Because of its excellent properties, modified starch can improve the quality of quick-frozen dumplings. At present, many studies have applied various chemical modified starch to quick-frozen dumplings, and studied its improvement effect on quick-frozen dumplings. Zhang Chenyun et al. (Zhang Chen et al., 2010, p. 29-31,34) studied the preparation of potato esterified starch and its application in quick-frozen dumplings.

Liu Yanqi, Liu Yaheng et al. (Liu Yanqi et al., 2008, p. 22-24) used Jinyuan dumpling powder as raw material, leek and pork as main filling materials, and phosphate starch as dough improver, the effects of phosphate starch with different substitution degree and addition amount on the freezing cracking rate and edible quality of quick-frozen dumplings were investigated. The results showed that the edible quality of quick-frozen dumplings was improved with the increase of phosphate starch content. Wang Qin, Li Jianwei, et al. (Wang Qin et al., 2005, p. 19-21) added different amounts of phosphate esterified starch to flour or glutinous rice flour to observe the anti freeze crack-

ing effect of dumplings and dumplings, and made sensory evaluation on the dumplings and glutinous rice ball. The effects of phosphate esterified starch on the freezing resistance of quick-frozen dumplings and glutinous rice ball were studied, the results showed that phosphate esterified starch could significantly improve the freeze cracking resistance of dumplings and glutinous rice ball, and the most suitable amount was 5%. Song Xiaoyan, Li Zhen et al. (Song Xiaoyan et al., 2010, p.182-185) studied the application of octenylsuccinate starch ester in quick-frozen dumplings.

The results showed that the transparency of waxy corn starch and rice starch paste was improved, and the freeze-thaw stability was improved. The results showed that the viscosity of flour was increased and the hardness, elasticity and chewiness of dumpling skin were improved by adding different proportions of waxy corn octenyl succinate starch ester and rice octenyl succinate starch ester ($P < 0.05$); the frozen cracking rate of dumplings with 5% pre gelatinized starch octenylsuccinate was the lowest, and the color, transparency, toughness and fineness of dumplings were the best. Zhang Zhong, Ren Yaqing (Zhang Zhong, Ren Yaqing, 2005, p. 39-42) obtained waxy corn carboxymethyl starch by carboxymethylation, and compared the application effect of waxy corn carboxymethyl starch, ordinary corn carboxymethyl starch and ordinary corn starch in quick-frozen dumplings.

At present, the quick-frozen food industry has become the fastest-growing emerging industry in the food industry. Among them, quick-frozen dumplings are the fastest-growing, accounting for 30% of the whole quick-frozen food industry, which is the largest type of quick-frozen food (Zhang Wenye, 2005). However, in the process of processing and circulation of quick-frozen dumplings, there will be a series of problems, such as frozen cracking of dumpling skin, water loss, browning of dumpling skin, broken belly during cooking, muddy soup, sticky taste, etc. Especially for crystal dumplings, because it is made of whole starch, it is easy to crack under the condition of $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, so it is very important to find a way to reduce its frost cracking rate. Because crystal dumpling skin is easy to crack and not easy to roll into shape in the production process, the surface is easy to crack, the skin is easy to open, the belly is broken, and the transparency is reduced. These problems will directly affect the sales status and shelf life of crystal dumplings, and it is difficult to meet people's life requirements. Therefore, how to improve the appearance, eating quality and processing performance of crystal dumplings is the food industry and many dumpling enterprises need to solve the problem. Boiled

dumplings have been studied in recent years. The results show that modified starch can improve the quality of boiled dumplings effectively because of its anti-aging, rheological properties, texture and cooking characteristics. As an improver, modified starch is widely used in dumplings, which can improve its transparency, water holding capacity, reduce frost cracking rate and cooking loss. In view of the current research on the application of modified starch in quick-frozen dumplings is more, and the application of modified starch in crystal dumplings is relatively small, therefore, the main research content of this subject is: the study of the properties of modified starch and its application in crystal dumpling skin. It mainly includes systematically learning and summarizing the properties of different modified starch, selecting several kinds of modified starch which can improve the properties of crystal dumpling skin. Through the determination and analysis of physical and chemical indexes, the modified starch which can improve the quality of crystal dumpling is selected (for example, it can make the dumpling skin not easy to crack and easy to roll into shape, increase transparency, reduce cooking loss, etc).

Materials and Methods. Four kinds of modified starch, namely potato acetate starch (MS1), potato hydroxypropyl starch (MS2), octenyl succinate starch sodium (MS3), acetate cassava starch (MS4), were screened through data integration and screening, and added to the raw material powder of crystal dumpling skin in different proportions. The physical indexes of the crystal dumpling (skin) were determined and analyzed, and then the most suitable modified starch, potato acetate starch, was selected.

Based on previous studies, four modified starches were selected to improve the quality of crystal dumpling skin. The swelling power, solubility, transparency, water holding capacity and gelatinization characteristics of different modified starches were studied;

The effects of the modified starch on the frost cracking rate, steaming loss and sensory quality of crystal dumpling skin were studied, and the modified starch which could improve the comprehensive quality of the product was analyzed and summarized.

Results and Discussion. *Water holding capacity of modified starch.* Water holding capacity reflects the ability of modified starch to maintain water under certain conditions. The water holding capacity of modified starch is related to the degree of hydrogen bond and covalent bond formed between starch chains (Berton B. et al., 2002, p. 326-331; Policegoudra R.S., Aradhya S.M., 2008, p. 513-519). The water holding capacity of raw starch and modified starch is shown in Fig. 3-3.

Figure 3-3 Water holding capacity of different raw starch and modified starch

Note: there are significant differences between different lowercase letters in the figure ($P < 0.05$)

It can be seen from Fig.3-3 that compared with the original mixed starch OS, modified starch MS1 and modified starch MS4 have higher water holding capacity, and modified starch MS4 has the best water holding capacity, indicating that the two acetate starch have better water holding capacity; while the water holding capacity of modified starch MS2 and MS3 is worse than that of original mixed starch, and modified starch MS2 has the worst water holding capacity.

Paste transparency of modified starch

Figure 3-4 Transmittance of different raw starch and modified starches

Note: there are significant differences between different lowercase letters in the figure ($P < 0.05$)

The transmittance of modified starch is shown in Fig. 3-4. It can be seen from the figure that the transmittance of the four modified starch is higher than that of the original mixed starch, which proves that the application of the modified starch to the crystal dumpling skin can improve its transparency is feasible. Among them, the transparency of modified starch MS2 is the highest, followed by modified starch MS3. Among the four kinds of modified starch, MS4 has the lowest transmittance, but it is still higher than the original starch. It lays a good foundation for the application of

these four kinds of modified starch in crystal dumpling skin to improve its transparency.

Determination of cortical structure characteristics of dumplings

According to the method of fan Qiliang and Ye Xiaofeng (Fan Qiliang, Zhang Xuan, 2014, p. 66-69; Ye Xiaofeng et al., 2013, p. 271-278.), the cooked starch peel was cooled for 5min and then determined by texture analyzer. Each sample is sampled three times and the average value is calculated. The specific parameter setting of physical property analyzer is shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The paramrter of texture analyzer

Parameter	Texture test	Shear test
Probe	P36R	HDP/BSK
Pattern	—	Compression
Velocity before measurement	2.0mm/s	2.0 mm/s
Test speed	0.8 mm/s	2.0 mm/s
Speed after measurement	0.8 mm/s	2.0 mm/s
Compression ratio /% or distance / mm	70%	20mm
Trigger value	Auto-0.05N	5.0g

Determination of frost cracking rate of quick frozen crystal dumplings

Refer to the method of Yi Cheng et al (Yi Cheng, Cheng Shenggao, 2007, p. 55-58). The prepared dumplings were put into the low-temperature refrigerator at -50°C for 30 min, and then the surface of the crystal

dumplings was observed. No matter the size and thickness of the cracks were regarded as cracks, the frost cracking rate of crystal dumplings was calculated according to formula 1.

$$\text{Cracking rate (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of frozen cracked dumplings}}{\text{Total number of dumplings}} \quad (1)$$

Sensory evaluation

According to SB /T 10138-1993 "wheat flour for dumplings" (SB /T 10138-1993) and combined with the actual situation, the sensory evaluation experiment of crystal dumpling skin was carried out in terms of transparency, brightness, apparent condition, elasticity, viscosity and fineness. The specific scoring standards are

shown in Table 2. The evaluation group is composed of 6 graduate students majoring in food science. The evaluators grade the frozen crystal dumpling skin according to various evaluation indexes. The average score of each index is taken as the sensory evaluation score. Finally, the scores of each index are added up to form the comprehensive score.

Table 2

Sensory evaluation of crystal dumpling skin			
Project	Full marks	Scoring criteria	
Appearance	Transparency	20	Transparent (13~20) ; Translucent (7~12) ; Opaque (0~6)
	Brightness	20	Bright (13~20) ; Commonly (7~12) ; Dim (0~6)
	Apparent situation	10	The surface is smooth and fine without bubbles (7~10) ; The surface is slightly soft and rotten, or there are a few bubbles (4~6) ; The surface is soft and rotten, or there are a lot of bubbles (0~3)
Texture	Elastic toughness	20	Soft and chewy (13~20) ; Commonly (7~12) ; Too soft or too hard, Poor elasticity (0~6)
	Viscosity	20	It's refreshing and doesn't stick to your teeth (13~20) ; Slightly sticky teeth (7~12) ; Stick teeth (0~6)
	Fineness	10	Exquisite (7~10) ; More delicate (4~6) ; Rough (0~3)

The effects of four kinds of modified starches (potato acetate starch, potato hydroxypropyl starch, octenyl succinate starch sodium, acetate cassava starch) on the quality of quick-frozen dumplings, including brightness, turbidity, transparency, texture characteristics, frost cracking rate and sensory quality were studied.

The results are as follows: The brightness of raw dumpling skin was significantly improved by adding modified starch at MS1-5%, MS1-15% and MS4-15%; Compared with the blank group, the transparency of dumpling skin with 10% MS4 was significantly higher than that of the blank group, i.e. the cooking loss rate was the lowest. There was no significant difference in the other MS4 addition levels and other three kinds of modified starch compared with the blank group; compared with the blank group, the addition levels of MS2-5%, MS2-10%, MS3-15%, MS4-5% and MS4-15% could improve the transparency of dumpling skin, the transparency of cooked crystal dumpling skin was significantly improved, and the level of MS3-15% was the highest. Other addition levels could not significantly improve the transparency of crystal dumpling skin; Adding modified starch of MS1-5%, MS1-10%, MS2-15%, MS3-10%, MS3-15% and MS4-10% could significantly improve the hardness of crystal dumpling skin; In terms of chewiness, the addition of MS1, MS2-15%, MS3-10% and MS3-15% could significantly improve the chewiness of crystal dumpling skin; For shear stress, MS1, MS2, MS3-10% and MS4-5% had no significant effect on shear stress, however, the chewiness of MS3

with other levels decreased significantly; With the increase of the amount of modified starch, except for MS2-5% and MS4-15% which were consistent with the blank group, the frozen cracking rate of the other dumplings with different types and levels of modified starch was lower than that of the blank group, and the frozen cracking rate of the dumplings added with MS1-15% was the lowest, which was 0; Sensory evaluation showed that compared with the blank group, the sensory scores of four groups with modified starch were higher than that of the blank group, and the sensory evaluation of crystal dumplings with MS2-5% addition level was the highest, and the scores from high to low were MS2-5%, MS1-15%, MS2-10%, MS3-10%.

Through the comprehensive analysis of the above indicators, it is concluded that the comprehensive quality of quick-frozen dumplings added with MS1-15% (15% potato acetate starch) is relatively good.

Conclusion. Compared with the original mixed powder, the light transmittance of the four modified starches is higher than that of the original mixed starch. Among them, potato hydroxypropyl starch has the highest transparency; among the four modified starches, acetate cassava starch has the lowest light transmittance but is still higher than the transparency of the original mixed starch. The research results of gelatinization characteristics show that: modified starch has a great influence on the gelatinization characteristics of the original mixture: the gelatinization temperature is increased,

and the remaining gelatinization parameters (peak viscosity, low viscosity, final viscosity, attenuation value, and retrogradation value) are reduced. This verifies the feasibility of the idea of applying these four modified starches to crystal dumpling skins, and at the same time provides a certain reference for related research on improving the characteristics of crystal dumpling skins.

Reference

1. Zhang Yanping. Manufacture and application of modified starch [M]. Beijing: Chemical Industry Press, 2007.
2. Zhang Chen Yun, Wang Na, Ren Xiaoqing. Preparation of potato esterified starch and its application in quick-frozen dumplings [J]. Food and feed industry. 2010, 7:29-31,34.
3. Liu Yanqi, Liu Yaheng, Li Changwen, et al. Effect of phosphate starch on the frozen cracking rate and edible quality of quick-frozen dumplings [J]. Food and feed industry. 2008, 12:22-24.
4. Wang Qin, Li Jianwei, Chen Xin. Study on improving the frost resistance of quick-frozen dumplings and dumplings [J]. Cold drinks and frozen food industry. 2005, 11 (3):19-21.
5. Song Xiaoyan, Li Zhen, Yang Nian, et al. Application of octenyl succinate starch ester in quick-frozen dumplings [J]. Food science. 2010, 31 (17):182-185.
6. Zhang Zhong, Ren Yaqing. Application of waxy corn carboxymethyl starch in quick-frozen dumplings [J]. Acta cerealis Sinica. 2005, 20 (4): 39-42.
7. Zhang Wenye. Processing technology and inspection of frozen convenient food [M]. Beijing: Chemical Industry Press, 2005.
8. Berton B., Scher J., Villieras F., et al. Measurement of hydration capacity of wheat flour: influence of composition and physical characteristics [J]. Power Technology, 2002, 128(2-3):326-331.
9. Policegoudra R.S., Aradhya S.M. Structure and biochemical properties of starch from an unconventional source - Mango ginger (*Curcuma amada* Roxb.) rhizome [J]. Food Hydrocolloids, 2008, 22(4):513-519.
10. Du shuangkui, Zhou Liqing, Yu Xiuzhu et al. Study on processing characteristics of yam starch [J]. Acta cerealis Sinica, 2010, 26 (3): 34-39.
11. Du Xianfeng, Xu Shiyang, Wang Zhang. Study on the transparency of starch paste and its influencing factors [J]. Acta agricultural engineering, 2002, 18 (1):129-132.
12. Fan Qiliang, Zhang Xuan. Study on the production technology and quality of rye flour dumpling skin [J]. Food science and technology and economy, 2014, 39 (6): 66-69.
13. Ye Xiaofeng, Han Yongbin, Zhao Liping, et al. Quality change and mechanism of frozen non fermented dough under freeze-thaw cycle [J]. Acta agricultural engineering, 2013, 29 (21): 271-278.
14. Yi Cheng, Cheng Shenggao. Study on processing technology and formula of quick frozen dumplings [J]. Modern food science and technology, 2007, 23 (7): 55-58.
15. SB /T 10138-1993, Wheat flour for dumplings [S].